

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Vesta Science LAMO (VSL) (vir_da023)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da023 session. These operations were executed as part of the VSL phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Vesta, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da023 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis et al., "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_vsl_99LAMO.r02.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsl_99LAMO.r02.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsl_S9LAM0.r02.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSL_VMLSTART_S9LAM0	386507892	386507894	2
VIR_VSL_C17FullCalibration_001	386507952	386520569	12617
VIR_VSL_C17OpenCover_001	386520852	386520892	40
VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001	386530074	386532426	2352
VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_001	386532474	386537275	4801
VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002	386564239	386565627	1388
VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_002	386566039	386570840	4801
VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003	386579072	386581424	2352
VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_003	386581472	386586273	4801
VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004	386595798	386597186	1388
VIR_VSL_C17CryocoolerOff_001	386597478	386597485	7
VIR_VSL_C17CloseCover_001	386600298	386600336	38
VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_004	386600418	386605219	4801
VIR_VSL_C17SAFEmode_001	386605218	386605339	121
VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOn_001	387145130	387155931	10801
VIR_VSL_C18OpenCover_001	387155930	387156270	340
VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001	387165191	387167543	2352
VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_001	387167591	387172392	4801
VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002	387183337	387184725	1388
VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_002	387185137	387189938	4801
VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003	387198481	387200833	2352
VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_003	387200881	387205682	4801
VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004	387215102	387216490	1388
VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOff_001	387216782	387216789	7
VIR_VSL_C18CloseCover_001	387219602	387219640	38
VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_004	387219722	387224523	4801
VIR_VSL_C18SAFEmode_001	387224522	387224643	121
VIR_VSL_VMLEND_S9LAM0	387224702	387224703	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Integrated sequence: da023b.00.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da023b.00.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 80 cubes for IR channel and 80 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

3. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

3.1 The sequence: vir_vsl_S9LAMO.r02.sasf

1	CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015\$\$MARK\$\$;	sasf
2	MISSION_NAME = DAWN;	
3	SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;	
4	DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;	
5	FILE_NAME = vir_vsl_S9LAMO.r02.sasf;	
6	APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2012-091T00:00:00.000;	

```

7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2012-101T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2012-065T17:51:16.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = SEQ;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsl_S9LAMO.r02;
11 HOST_ID = dawnjpldsc;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   DWN DSC team account
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Mon Mar  5 17:51:16 2012
20 *seqgenCore V32.0 Tue Dec 14 17:21:23 PST 2010
21 *BEGIN      2012-091T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2012-101T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_VSL_da023_Sequence_9
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *SEQ_VSL_C17TurnToEarth_001, 2012-093T12:15:00.000
26 *SEQ_VSL_C17TurnToEarth_002, 2012-094T23:15:00.000
27 *SEQ_VSL_C18TurnToEarth_001, 2012-100T12:15:00.000
28 *SEQ_VSL_C18TurnToEarth_002, 2012-101T23:15:00.000
29 *VSL_DLTERM_611, 2012-092T00:34:12.000
30 *VSL_DLTERM_612, 2012-092T04:57:54.000
31 *VSL_DLTERM_614, 2012-092T13:47:19.000
32 *VSL_DLTERM_615, 2012-092T18:09:32.000
33 *VSL_DLTERM_616, 2012-092T22:33:18.000
34 *VSL_DLTERM_651, 2012-099T08:58:50.000
35 *VSL_DLTERM_652, 2012-099T13:23:11.000
36 *VSL_DLTERM_653, 2012-099T17:45:37.000
37 *VSL_DLTERM_654, 2012-099T22:13:01.000
38 *VSL_DLTERM_655, 2012-100T02:35:02.000
39 *EPOCHS_END
40 *Input files used:
41 *File Type  Last modified      File name
42 *SC_MODEL   Tue Aug 16 20:43:44 2011 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/smf/
dawn.cd1.FDAWN_9_ODDAWN_9_0_0_2011Aug16_20_55_5.smf
43 *CATALOG    Tue Aug 30 23:35:33 2011 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/
dawn.cd1.FDAWN_9_ODDAWN_9_0_0_2011Aug30_1500_1.satf
44 *LEGENDS    Tue May 11 21:36:07 1999 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/legend/Dawn.1.0.legend
45 *CATALOG    Thu Mar 24 16:44:44 2011 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/
dawn.blk.d_fb20_eng_blib_mod.900.r4.satf
46 *CATALOG    Thu May 20 15:12:56 2010 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/
dawn.blk.d_fb19_sci_blib_mod.900.r3.satf
47 *CATALOG    Thu May 20 15:12:39 2010 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/satf/
dawn.blk.d_fb17_safe_blib_mod.900.r2.satf
48 *CONTEXT    Thu May 24 20:41:12 2007 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/dawn.sct.cvf
49 *CONTEXT    Tue Apr 12 23:15:45 2011 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/dawn.cvf
50 *CONTEXT    Mon Mar 12 17:15:57 2007 /delivery/MSOP/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq/cvf/msop.soe.cvf
51 *CONTEXT    Mon Apr 21 19:28:05 2003 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/
msop.dsn.cvf
52 *CONTEXT    Thu Aug  4 18:09:05 2011 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/
soe_defaults_203.cvf
53 *CONTEXT    Thu Aug  2 15:59:05 2007 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_config/dsn_config/
dsn_config.cvf
54 *CLOCK      Tue Jan 13 18:47:17 2009 /delivery/MSOPRW/J6.7.1-DAWN/seq_rw/seq_input/sclk/
DAWN_203_PSCLKSCET.00002
55 *SEQUENCE   Mon Mar  5 17:51:16 2012 /export/home/dwndsc/dsc/sequencing/vesta/vsl/da023/vir/r02/
vir_vsl_S9LAMO.r02.sasf

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```
56 *ALLOCATION
57 *BG_SEQUENCE
58 *CAT_NO_VML
59 *CONDITIONS
60 *DEFINITION
61 *DEP_CONTEXT
62 *EVENTS
63 *LIGHTTIME
64 *MASK
65 *OPTG_FD
66 *GEOMETRY
67 *REDUNDANT
68 *REQUESTS
69 *RESOLUTION
70 *RULES
71 *SCRIPT
72 *ON_BOARD_SE
73 *TELEMETRY
74 *TYPEDEF
75 *VIEWPERIOD
76 *VIEW_FD
77 *****
78 $$EOH
79 $$EOD
80 request(VIR_VSL_VMLSTART_S9LAM0,
81     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_611-01:16:00,
82     TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_vsl_S9LAM0 (ds098)",
83     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
84     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
85     KEY, "No_Key")
86
87 activity(1,
88     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
89     SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","vir_vsl_S9LAM0","vi
fb04")
90 ),
91 note(1,
92     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
93     TEXT,\ "Begin sequence ds098 - vir_vsl_S9LAM0"\
94 ),
95 end;
96
97 request(VIR_VSL_C17FullCalibration_001,
98     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_611-01:15:00,
99     TITLE, "VIR cooldown and full calibration sequence",
100    REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
101    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
102    KEY, "No_Key")
103
104 spawn(1,
105     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
106     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
107     RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)
108 ),
109 command(1,
110     SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
111     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17FullCalibration_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
```

```
112 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
113 ),
114 note(1,
115 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
116 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17FullCalibration_001: Full Calibration VML is finished.\"\
117 ),
118 note(2,
119 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
120 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17FullCalibration_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960 packets.\"\
121 ),
122 end;
123
124 request(VIR_VSL_C17OpenCover_001,
125 START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_611+02:20:00,
126 TITLE, "VIR open cover",
127 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
128 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
129 KEY, "No_Key")
130
131 activity(1,
132 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
133 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17OpenCover_001: Set for opening the cover.\"\,
134 VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
135 ),
136 end;
137
138 request(VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001,
139 START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_612+00:30:00,
140 TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
141 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
142 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
143 KEY, "No_Key")
144
145 command(1,
146 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
147 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
148 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\,
149 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
150 ),
151 command(2,
152 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
153 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
154 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
155 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
156 ),
157 command(3,
158 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
159 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
160 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
161 ),
162 note(1,
163 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
164 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit\"\
165 ),
166 command(4,
167 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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167 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
168 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
169 ),
170 command(5,
171 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
172 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
173 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
174 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
175 ),
176 command(6,
177 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
178 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
179 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
180 ),
181 note(2,
182 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
183 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
184 ),
185 command(7,
186 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
187 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
188 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
189 ),
190 command(8,
191 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
192 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
193 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
194 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
195 ),
196 command(9,
197 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
198 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
199 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
200 ),
201 note(3,
202 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
203 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit"\
204 ),
205 command(10,
206 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
207 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
208 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
209 ),
210 command(11,
211 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
212 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
213 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
214 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
215 ),
216 command(12,
217 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
218 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
```

```
219     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
220   ),
221   note(4,
222     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
223     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
224   ),
225   command(13,
226     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
227     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
228     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
229   ),
230   command(14,
231     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
232     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
233     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
234     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
235   ),
236   command(15,
237     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
238     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
239     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
240   ),
241   note(5,
242     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
243     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit"\
244   ),
245   command(16,
246     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
247     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
248     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
249   ),
250   command(17,
251     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
252     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
253     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
254     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
255   ),
256   command(18,
257     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
259     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
260   ),
261   note(6,
262     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
264   ),
265   command(19,
266     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
267     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
268     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
269   ),
270   command(20,
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271     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
272     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
273     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
274     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
275 ),
276     command(21,
277     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
278     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
279     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
280 ),
281     note(7,
282     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
283     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit\"\\
284 ),
285     command(22,
286     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
287     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
288     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
289 ),
290     command(23,
291     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
292     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
293     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
294     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
295 ),
296     command(24,
297     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
298     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
299     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
300 ),
301     note(8,
302     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
303     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
304 ),
305     command(25,
306     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
307     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
308     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
309 ),
310     command(26,
311     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
312     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
313     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
314     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
315 ),
316     command(27,
317     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
318     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
319     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
320 ),
321     note(9,
322     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
323     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit\"\\
324 ),
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325  command(28,  
326    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
327    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
    frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
328    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
329  ),  
330  command(29,  
331    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
332    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
333    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
334    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
335  ),  
336  command(30,  
337    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
338    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
339    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
340  ),  
341  note(10,  
342    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
343    TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\  
344  ),  
345  command(31,  
346    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
347    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
    frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
348    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
349  ),  
350  command(32,  
351    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
352    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
353    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
354    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
355  ),  
356  command(33,  
357    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
358    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
359    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
360  ),  
361  note(11,  
362    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
363    TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit"\  
364  ),  
365  command(34,  
366    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
367    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
    frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
368    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
369  ),  
370  command(35,  
371    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
372    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
373    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
374    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
375  ),  
376  command(36,
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377     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
378     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
379     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
380 ),
381 note(12,
382     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
383     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
384 ),
385 command(37,
386     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
387     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
388     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
389     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
390 ),
391 command(38,
392     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
393     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
394     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
395     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
396 ),
397 command(39,
398     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
399     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
400     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
401 ),
402 note(13,
403     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
404     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit\"\\
405 ),
406 command(40,
407     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
408     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
409     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
410     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
411 ),
412 command(41,
413     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
414     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
415     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
416     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
417 ),
418 command(42,
419     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
420     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
421     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
422 ),
423 note(14,
424     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
425     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit\"\\
426 ),
427 command(43,
428     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
429     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
430     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
431     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
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429 ),
430 command(44,
431   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
432   COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
433   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
434   VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
435 ),
436 command(45,
437   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
438   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
439   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
440 ),
441 note(15,
442   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
443   TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit\"\\
444 ),
445 command(46,
446   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
447   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
448   frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
449   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
450 ),
451 command(47,
452   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
453   COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
454   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
455   VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
456 ),
457 command(48,
458   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
459   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
460   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
461 ),
462 note(16,
463   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
464   TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
465 ),
466 end;
467 request(VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_001,
468   START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_612+01:10:00,
469   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
470   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
471   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
472   KEY, \"No_Key\")
473
474 command(1,
475   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
476   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
477   VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
478 ),
479 command(2,
480   SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
481   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
482   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
483 ),
484 note(1,
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485     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
486     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.635 Gibit.\"\\
487   ),
488   end;
489
490   request(VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002,
491     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_614+01:10:00,
492     TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
493     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
494     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
495     KEY, \"No_Key\")
496
497   command(1,
498     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
499     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
500     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
501     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
502   ),
503   command(2,
504     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
505     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
506     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
507     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
508   ),
509   command(3,
510     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
511     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
512     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
513   ),
514   note(1,
515     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
516     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
517   ),
518   command(4,
519     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
520     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
521     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
522     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
523   ),
524   command(5,
525     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
526     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
527     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
528     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
529   ),
530   command(6,
531     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
532     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
533     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
534   ),
535   note(2,
536     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
537     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
538   ),
539   command(7,
540     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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539 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
540 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
541 ),
542 command(8,
543 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
544 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
545 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
546 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
547 ),
548 command(9,
549 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
550 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
551 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
552 ),
553 note(3,
554 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
555 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
556 ),
557 command(10,
558 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
559 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
560 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
561 ),
562 command(11,
563 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
564 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
565 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
566 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
567 ),
568 command(12,
569 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
570 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
571 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
572 ),
573 note(4,
574 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
575 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
576 ),
577 end;
578
579 request(VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_002,
580 START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_614+01:40:00,
581 TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
582 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
583 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
584 KEY, "No_Key")
585
586 command(1,
587 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
588 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
589 VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
590 ),
591 command(2,
592 SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,

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593     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
594     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
595   ),
596   note(1,
597     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
598     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.145 Gibit."\\
599   ),
600   end;
601
602   request(VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003,
603     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_615+00:55:00,
604     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
605     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
606     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
607     KEY, "No_Key")
608
609   command(1,
610     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
611     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
612     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\\,
613     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
614   ),
615   command(2,
616     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
617     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
618     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
619     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
620   ),
621   command(3,
622     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
623     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
624     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
625   ),
626   note(1,
627     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
628     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit"\\
629   ),
630   command(4,
631     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
632     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
633     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\\,
634     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
635   ),
636   command(5,
637     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
638     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
639     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
640     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
641   ),
642   command(6,
643     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
644     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
645     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
646   ),
647   note(2,
```

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647     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
648   ),
649   command(7,
650     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
651     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
        frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
652     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
653   ),
654   command(8,
655     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
656     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
657     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
658     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
659   ),
660   command(9,
661     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
662     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
663     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
664   ),
665   note(3,
666     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
667     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit"\
668   ),
669   command(10,
670     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
671     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
        frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
672     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
673   ),
674   command(11,
675     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
676     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
677     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
678     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
679   ),
680   command(12,
681     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
682     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
683     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
684   ),
685   note(4,
686     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
687     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
688   ),
689   command(13,
690     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
691     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
        frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
692     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
693   ),
694   command(14,
695     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
696     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
697     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
698     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
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699 ),
700   command(15,
701     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
702     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
703     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
704   ),
705   note(5,
706     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
707     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit\"\\
708   ),
709   command(16,
710     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
711     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
712     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
713     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
714   ),
715   command(17,
716     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
717     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
718     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
719     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
720   ),
721   command(18,
722     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
723     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
724     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
725   ),
726   note(6,
727     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
728     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit\"\\
729   ),
730   command(19,
731     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
732     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
733     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
734     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
735   ),
736   command(20,
737     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
738     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
739     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
740     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
741   ),
742   command(21,
743     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
744     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
745     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
746   ),
747   note(7,
748     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
749     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit\"\\
750   ),
751   command(22,
752     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
753     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
754     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
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752     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
753 ),
754     command(23,
755     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
756     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
757     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
758     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
759 ),
760     command(24,
761     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
762     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
763     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
764 ),
765     note(8,
766     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
767     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\
768 ),
769     command(25,
770     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
771     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\,
772     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
773 ),
774     command(26,
775     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
776     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
777     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
778     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
779 ),
780     command(27,
781     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
782     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
783     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
784 ),
785     note(9,
786     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
787     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit\"\
788 ),
789     command(28,
790     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
791     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\,
792     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
793 ),
794     command(29,
795     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
796     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
797     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
798     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
799 ),
800     command(30,
801     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
802     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
803     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
804 ),
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805 note(10,  
806   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
807   TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\  
808 ),  
809 command(31,  
810   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
811   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
812   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
813 ),  
814 command(32,  
815   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
816   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
817   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
818   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
819 ),  
820 command(33,  
821   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
822   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
823   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
824 ),  
825 note(11,  
826   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
827   TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit"\  
828 ),  
829 command(34,  
830   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
831   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
832   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
833 ),  
834 command(35,  
835   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
836   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
837   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
838   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
839 ),  
840 command(36,  
841   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
842   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
843   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
844 ),  
845 note(12,  
846   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
847   TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\  
848 ),  
849 command(37,  
850   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
851   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C170sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
852   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
853 ),  
854 command(38,  
855   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
856   COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
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857     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
858     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
859 ),
860     command(39,
861     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
862     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
863     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
864 ),
865     note(13,
866     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
867     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit"\
868 ),
869     command(40,
870     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
871     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
872     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
873     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
874 ),
875     command(41,
876     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
877     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
878     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
879     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
880 ),
881     command(42,
882     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
883     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
884     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
885 ),
886     note(14,
887     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
888     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit"\
889 ),
890     command(43,
891     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
892     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
893     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
894     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
895 ),
896     command(44,
897     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
898     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
899     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
900     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
901 ),
902     command(45,
903     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
904     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
905     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
906 ),
907     note(15,
908     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
909     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit"\
910 ),
911     command(46,
912     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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911 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
912 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
913 ),
914 command(47,
915 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
916 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
917 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
918 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
919 ),
920 command(48,
921 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
922 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
923 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
924 ),
925 note(16,
926 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
927 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
928 ),
929 end;
930
931 request(VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_003,
932 START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_615+01:35:00,
933 TITLE,"VIR dump data into VR4",
934 REQUESTOR,"sfonte",
935 PROCESSOR,"GSC1",
936 KEY,"No_Key")
937
938 command(1,
939 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
940 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
941 VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
942 ),
943 command(2,
944 SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
945 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
946 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
947 ),
948 note(1,
949 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
950 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 1.655 Gibit."\
951 ),
952 end;
953
954 request(VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004,
955 START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_616+01:10:00,
956 TITLE,"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
957 REQUESTOR,"sfonte",
958 PROCESSOR,"GSC1",
959 KEY,"No_Key")
960
961 command(1,
962 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
963 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
964 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
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965 ),
966   command(2,
967     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
968     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
969     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
970     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
971   ),
972   command(3,
973     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
974     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
975     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
976   ),
977   note(1,
978     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
979     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
980   ),
981   command(4,
982     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
983     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
984     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
985     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
986   ),
987   command(5,
988     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
989     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
990     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
991     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
992   ),
993   command(6,
994     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
995     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
996     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
997   ),
998   note(2,
999     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1000    TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
1001  ),
1002  command(7,
1003    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1004    NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1005    frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1006    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1007  ),
1008  command(8,
1009    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1010    COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1011    NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1012    VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1013  ),
1014  command(9,
1015    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1016    NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1017    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1018  ),
1019  note(3,
1020    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1019 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\
1020 ),
1021 command(10,
1022 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1023 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1024 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1025 ),
1026 command(11,
1027 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1028 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1029 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1030 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1031 ),
1032 command(12,
1033 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1034 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1035 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1036 ),
1037 note(4,
1038 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1039 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
1040 ),
1041 end;
1042
1043 request(VIR_VSL_C17CryocoolerOff_001,
1044 START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_616+01:38:00,
1045 TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
1046 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1047 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1048 KEY, "No_Key")
1049
1050 command(1,
1051 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1052 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1053 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1054 ),
1055 command(2,
1056 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1057 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.""\,
1058 VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
1059 ),
1060 note(1,
1061 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1062 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C17CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off.""\
1063 ),
1064 end;
1065
1066 request(VIR_VSL_C17CloseCover_001,
1067 START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_616+02:25:00,
1068 TITLE, "VIR close cover",
1069 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1070 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1071 KEY, "No_Key")
1072
1073 activity(1,
1074 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,

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1075     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover." \ ,
1076     VIR_Cover(vir_cover, "CLOSE")
1077   ),
1078 end;
1079
1080 request(VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_004,
1081     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_616+02:27:00,
1082     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1083     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1084     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1085     KEY, "No_Key")
1086
1087     command(1,
1088         SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:00 \ , FROM_REQUEST_START,
1089         NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4." \ ,
1090         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1091     ),
1092     command(2,
1093         SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 01:19:55 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1094         NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
1095         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1096     ),
1097     note(1,
1098         SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1099         TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 2.165 Gibit." \
1100     ),
1101 end;
1102
1103 request(VIR_VSL_C17SAFEmode_001,
1104     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_616+03:47:00,
1105     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
1106     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1107     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1108     KEY, "No_Key")
1109
1110     command(1,
1111         SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:00 \ , FROM_REQUEST_START,
1112         NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17SAFEmode_001: changing VIR mode into SAFE" \ ,
1113         VIR_SAFE()
1114     ),
1115     command(2,
1116         SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:01:00 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1117         NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17SAFEmode_001: dump the error log information" \ ,
1118         VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
1119     ),
1120     note(1,
1121         SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:01:00 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1122         TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C17SAFEmode_001: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced" \
1123     ),
1124 end;
1125
1126 request(VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOn_001,
1127     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_651-00:40:00,
1128     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
1129     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1130     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1131     KEY, "No_Key")
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1132
1133   command(1,
1134     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1135     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18Cryocooler0n_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1136     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1137   ),
1138   command(2,
1139     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1140     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18Cryocooler0n_001: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\\,
1141     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",75,0)
1142   ),
1143   note(1,
1144     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1145     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18Cryocooler0n_001: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
1146     waiting."\\
1147   ),
1148 end;
1149 request(VIR_VSL_C180penCover_001,
1150   START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_651+02:20:00,
1151   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1152   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1153   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1154   KEY, "No_Key")
1155
1156   command(1,
1157     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1158     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180penCover_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\\,
1159     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1160   ),
1161   activity(1,
1162     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1163     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180penCover_001: Set for opening the cover."\\,
1164     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1165   ),
1166 end;
1167
1168 request(VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001,
1169   START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_652+00:30:00,
1170   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1171   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1172   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1173   KEY, "No_Key")
1174
1175   command(1,
1176     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1177     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1178     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\\,
1179     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1180   ),
1181   command(2,
1182     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1183     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1184     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1185     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1186   ),
1187   command(3,
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1187     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1188     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1189     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1190 ),
1191     note(1,
1192     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1193     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit\"\\
1194     ),
1195     command(4,
1196     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1197     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1198     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1199     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1200     ),
1201     command(5,
1202     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1203     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1204     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1205     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1206     ),
1207     command(6,
1208     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1209     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1210     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1211     ),
1212     note(2,
1213     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1214     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit\"\\
1215     ),
1216     command(7,
1217     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1218     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1219     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1220     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1221     ),
1222     command(8,
1223     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1224     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1225     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1226     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1227     ),
1228     command(9,
1229     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1230     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1231     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1232     ),
1233     note(3,
1234     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1235     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit\"\\
1236     ),
1237     command(10,
1238     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1239     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1240     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1241     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
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1239 ),
1240 command(11,
1241   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1242   COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1243   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1244   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1245 ),
1246 command(12,
1247   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1248   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1249   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1250 ),
1251 note(4,
1252   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1253   TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\
1254 ),
1255 command(13,
1256   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1257   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1258   frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",\
1259   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1260 ),
1261 command(14,
1262   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1263   COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1264   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1265   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1266 ),
1267 command(15,
1268   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1269   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1270   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1271 ),
1272 note(5,
1273   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1274   TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit\"\
1275 ),
1276 command(16,
1277   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1278   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1279   frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",\
1280   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1281 ),
1282 command(17,
1283   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1284   COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1285   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1286   VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1287 ),
1288 command(18,
1289   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1290   NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1291   VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1292 ),
1293 note(6,
1294   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1293 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
1294 ),
1295 command(19,
1296 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1297 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1298 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1299 ),
1300 command(20,
1301 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1302 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1303 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1304 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1305 ),
1306 command(21,
1307 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1308 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1309 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1310 ),
1311 note(7,
1312 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1313 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit"\
1314 ),
1315 command(22,
1316 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1317 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1318 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1319 ),
1320 command(23,
1321 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1322 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1323 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1324 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1325 ),
1326 command(24,
1327 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1328 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1329 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1330 ),
1331 note(8,
1332 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1333 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
1334 ),
1335 command(25,
1336 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1337 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1338 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1339 ),
1340 command(26,
1341 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1342 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1343 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1344 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
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1345 ),
1346   command(27,
1347     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1348     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1349     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1350   ),
1351   note(9,
1352     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1353     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit\"\\
1354   ),
1355   command(28,
1356     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1357     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1358     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1359     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1360   ),
1361   command(29,
1362     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1363     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1364     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1365     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1366   ),
1367   command(30,
1368     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1369     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1370     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1371   ),
1372   note(10,
1373     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1374     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit\"\\
1375   ),
1376   command(31,
1377     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1378     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1379     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1380     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1381   ),
1382   command(32,
1383     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1384     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1385     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1386     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1387   ),
1388   command(33,
1389     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1390     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1391     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1392   ),
1393   note(11,
1394     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1395     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit\"\\
1396   ),
1397   command(34,
1398     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1399     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1400     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
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1398     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1399 ),
1400 command(35,
1401     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1402     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
1403     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
1404     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1405 ),
1406 command(36,
1407     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1408     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
1409     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1410 ),
1411 note(12,
1412     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1413     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\
1414 ),
1415 command(37,
1416     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1417     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\,
1418     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1419 ),
1420 command(38,
1421     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1422     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
1423     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
1424     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1425 ),
1426 command(39,
1427     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1428     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
1429     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1430 ),
1431 note(13,
1432     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1433     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit\"\
1434 ),
1435 command(40,
1436     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1437     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\,
1438     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1439 ),
1440 command(41,
1441     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1442     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\,
1443     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\,
1444     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1445 ),
1446 command(42,
1447     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1448     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\",
1449     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1450 ),
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1451 note(14,  
1452   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1453   TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit"\  
1454 ),  
1455 command(43,  
1456   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1457   NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1458   VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
1459 ),  
1460   command(44,  
1461     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1462     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1463     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1464     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1465   ),  
1466   command(45,  
1467     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1468     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1469     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1470   ),  
1471   note(15,  
1472     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1473     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit"\  
1474   ),  
1475   command(46,  
1476     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1477     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1478     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
1479   ),  
1480   command(47,  
1481     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1482     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1483     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1484     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1485   ),  
1486   command(48,  
1487     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1488     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1489     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1490   ),  
1491   note(16,  
1492     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1493     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\  
1494   ),  
1495 end;  
1496  
1497 request(VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_001,  
1498   START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_652+01:10:00,  
1499   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
1500   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1501   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1502   KEY, "No_Key")  
1503  
1504 command(1,
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1505     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1506     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1507     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1508 ),
1509     command(2,
1510     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1511     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1512     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1513 ),
1514     note(1,
1515     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1516     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.510 Gibit.\"\\
1517 ),
1518 end;
1519
1520 request(VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002,
1521     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_653+01:10:00,
1522     TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
1523     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1524     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1525     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1526
1527     command(1,
1528     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1529     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1530     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1531     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1532 ),
1533     command(2,
1534     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1535     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1536     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1537     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1538 ),
1539     command(3,
1540     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1541     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1542     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1543 ),
1544     note(1,
1545     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1546     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
1547 ),
1548     command(4,
1549     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1550     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1551     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1552     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1553 ),
1554     command(5,
1555     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1556     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1557     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1558     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1559 ),
1560     command(6,
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1559     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1560     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1561     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1562   ),
1563   note(2,
1564     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1565     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\\
1566   ),
1567   command(7,
1568     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1569     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1570     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
1571     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1572   ),
1573   command(8,
1574     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1575     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1576     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1577     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1578   ),
1579   command(9,
1580     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1581     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1582     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1583   ),
1584   note(3,
1585     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1586     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\\
1587   ),
1588   command(10,
1589     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1590     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1591     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
1592     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1593   ),
1594   command(11,
1595     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1596     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
1597     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
1598     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1599   ),
1600   command(12,
1601     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1602     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1603     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1604   ),
1605   note(4,
1606     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1607     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\\
1608   ),
1609   end;
1610   request(VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_002,
1611     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_653+01:40:00,
1612     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1613     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
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1613     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1614     KEY, "No_Key")
1615
1616     command(1,
1617     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1618     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
1619     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1620     ),
1621     command(2,
1622     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1623     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1624     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1625     ),
1626     note(1,
1627     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1628     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.019 Gibit." \
1629     ),
1630 end;
1631
1632 request(VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003,
1633     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_654+00:55:00,
1634     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1635     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1636     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1637     KEY, "No_Key")
1638
1639     command(1,
1640     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1641     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \,
1642     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VIR_TM
1643     ),
1644     command(2,
1645     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1646     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1647     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1648     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1649     ),
1650     command(3,
1651     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1652     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1653     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1654     ),
1655     note(1,
1656     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1657     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit" \
1658     ),
1659     command(4,
1660     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1661     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \,
1662     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VIR_TM
1663     ),
1664     command(5,
1665     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1666     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
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1667 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1668 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1669 ),
1670 command(6,
1671 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1672 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1673 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1674 ),
1675 note(2,
1676 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1677 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
1678 ),
1679 command(7,
1680 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1681 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1682 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1683 ),
1684 command(8,
1685 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1686 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1687 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1688 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1689 ),
1690 command(9,
1691 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1692 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1693 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1694 ),
1695 note(3,
1696 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1697 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit"\
1698 ),
1699 command(10,
1700 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1701 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1702 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1703 ),
1704 command(11,
1705 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1706 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1707 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1708 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1709 ),
1710 command(12,
1711 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1712 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
1713 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1714 ),
1715 note(4,
1716 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1717 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
1718 ),
1719 command(13,
1720 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1721 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1722 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1723 ),
1724 command(14,
1725 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1726 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1727 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1728 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1729 ),
1730 command(15,
1731 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1732 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1733 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1734 ),
1735 note(5,
1736 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1737 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit"\
1738 ),
1739 command(16,
1740 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1741 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1742 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1743 ),
1744 command(17,
1745 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1746 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1747 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1748 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1749 ),
1750 command(18,
1751 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1752 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1753 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1754 ),
1755 note(6,
1756 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1757 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
1758 ),
1759 command(19,
1760 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1761 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1762 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1763 ),
1764 command(20,
1765 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1766 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1767 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1768 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1769 ),
1770 command(21,
1771 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1772 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
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1773 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1774 ),
1775 note(7,
1776 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1777 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit"\
1778 ),
1779 command(22,
1780 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1781 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1782 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1783 ),
1784 command(23,
1785 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1786 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1787 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1788 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1789 ),
1790 command(24,
1791 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1792 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1793 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1794 ),
1795 note(8,
1796 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1797 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
1798 ),
1799 command(25,
1800 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1801 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1802 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1803 ),
1804 command(26,
1805 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1806 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1807 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1808 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1809 ),
1810 command(27,
1811 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1812 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
1813 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1814 ),
1815 note(9,
1816 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1817 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit"\
1818 ),
1819 command(28,
1820 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1821 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1822 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1823 ),
1824 command(29,
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1825     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1826     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1827     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1828     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1829 ),
1830     command(30,
1831     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1832     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1833     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1834 ),
1835     note(10,
1836     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1837     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit\"\\
1838 ),
1839     command(31,
1840     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1841     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1842     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1843 ),
1844     command(32,
1845     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1846     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1847     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1848     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1849 ),
1850     command(33,
1851     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1852     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1853     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1854 ),
1855     note(11,
1856     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1857     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit\"\\
1858 ),
1859     command(34,
1860     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1861     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1862     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR_TM
1863 ),
1864     command(35,
1865     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1866     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1867     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1868     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1869 ),
1870     command(36,
1871     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1872     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1873     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1874 ),
1875     note(12,
1876     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1877     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
1878 ),
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1879  command(37,  
1880    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1881    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
    frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
1882    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
1883  ),  
1884  command(38,  
1885    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1886    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
1887    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
1888    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1889  ),  
1890  command(39,  
1891    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1892    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
1893    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1894  ),  
1895  note(13,  
1896    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1897    TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit"\  
1898  ),  
1899  command(40,  
1900    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1901    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
    frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
1902    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
1903  ),  
1904  command(41,  
1905    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1906    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
1907    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
1908    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1909  ),  
1910  command(42,  
1911    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1912    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,  
1913    VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1914  ),  
1915  note(14,  
1916    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1917    TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit"\  
1918  ),  
1919  command(43,  
1920    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1921    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50  
    frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,  
1922    VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
1923  ),  
1924  command(44,  
1925    SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1926    COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
1927    NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C180sPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
1928    VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1929  ),  
1930  command(45,
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1931     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1932     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1933     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1934 ),
1935     note(15,
1936     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1937     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit\"\\
1938     ),
1939     command(46,
1940     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1941     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2 detector,50
1942     frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1943     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1944     ),
1945     command(47,
1946     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1947     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1948     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1949     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1950     ),
1951     command(48,
1952     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1953     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1954     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1955     ),
1956     note(16,
1957     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1958     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
1959     ),
1960     end;
1961     request(VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_003,
1962     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_654+01:35:00,
1963     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1964     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1965     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1966     KEY, "No_Key")
1967
1968     command(1,
1969     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1970     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1971     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1972     ),
1973     command(2,
1974     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1975     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1976     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1977     ),
1978     note(1,
1979     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1980     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 1.529 Gibit.\"\\
1981     ),
1982     end;
1983
1984     request(VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004,
1985     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_655+01:10:00,
1986     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",

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1987 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1988 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1989 KEY, "No_Key")
1990
1991 command(1,
1992 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1993 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
1994 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
1995 ),
1996 command(2,
1997 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1998 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1999 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2000 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2001 ),
2002 command(3,
2003 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2004 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2005 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2006 ),
2007 note(1,
2008 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2009 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
2010 ),
2011 command(4,
2012 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2013 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2014 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2015 ),
2016 command(5,
2017 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2018 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
2019 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
2020 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2021 ),
2022 command(6,
2023 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2024 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
2025 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2026 ),
2027 note(2,
2028 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2029 TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
2030 ),
2031 command(7,
2032 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2033 NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
2034 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM
2035 ),
2036 command(8,
2037 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2038 COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
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2039 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
2040 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
2041 ),  
2042 command(9,  
2043 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2044 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
2045 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
2046 ),  
2047 note(3,  
2048 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2049 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\  
2050 ),  
2051 command(10,  
2052 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2053 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50  
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,  
2054 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR_TM  
2055 ),  
2056 command(11,  
2057 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2058 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,  
2059 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
2060 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
2061 ),  
2062 command(12,  
2063 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2064 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
2065 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
2066 ),  
2067 note(4,  
2068 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2069 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\  
2070 ),  
2071 end;  
2072  
2073 request(VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOff_001,  
2074 START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_655+01:38:00,  
2075 TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",  
2076 REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
2077 PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
2078 KEY, "No_Key")  
2079  
2080 command(1,  
2081 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2082 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
2083 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
2084 ),  
2085 command(2,  
2086 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2087 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\  
2088 VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)  
2089 ),  
2090 note(1,  
2091 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2092 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C18CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off."\  
2093 ),  
2094 end;
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2095
2096 request(VIR_VSL_C18CloseCover_001,
2097     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_655+02:25:00,
2098     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
2099     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2100     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2101     KEY, "No_Key")
2102
2103 activity(1,
2104     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2105     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover." \,
2106     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
2107 ),
2108 end;
2109
2110 request(VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_004,
2111     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_655+02:27:00,
2112     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
2113     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2114     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2115     KEY, "No_Key")
2116
2117 command(1,
2118     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2119     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
2120     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
2121 ),
2122 command(2,
2123     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2124     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
2125     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2126 ),
2127 note(1,
2128     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2129     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 2.039 Gibit." \
2130 ),
2131 end;
2132
2133 request(VIR_VSL_C18SAFEmode_001,
2134     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_655+03:47:00,
2135     TITLE, "VIR Safe",
2136     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2137     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2138     KEY, "No_Key")
2139
2140 command(1,
2141     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2142     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18SAFEmode_001: changing VIR mode into SAFE" \,
2143     VIR_SAFE()
2144 ),
2145 command(2,
2146     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2147     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C18SAFEmode_001: dump the error log information" \,
2148     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
2149 ),
2150 note(1,
2151     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
```

```
2152     TEXT, \"VIR_VSL_C18SAFEmode_001: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced\"\  
2153   ),  
2154 end;  
2155  
2156 request(VIR_VSL_VMLEND_S9LAM0,  
2157     START_TIME, VSL_DLTERM_655+03:50:00,  
2158     TITLE, \"VIR Sequence End - vir_vsl_S9LAM0 (ds098)\",  
2159     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
2160     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
2161     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
2162  
2163   note(1,  
2164     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00, FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2165     TEXT, \"End sequence ds098 - vir_vsl_S9LAM0\"\  
2166   ),  
2167 end;  
2168  
2169 $$EOF
```